

Conference: Online, 15-18 March 2021
Conference Director: Tristan Loraine
Publisher: London, UK: GCAQE (<https://gcaqe.org>)
Editors: Dieter Scholz, Susan Michaelis

Air Accident Bureau Incident Reports - Case Study Review

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the work reviewed in this short paper was to evaluate some of the common aspects highlighted in bureau of air safety investigations related to aircraft air supply fume events.

Methodology: An aircraft incident investigation report by the UK based Air Accidents Investigation Branch (AAIB) was examined, involving fume events reported on the A320 group of aircraft. The aim was to align the report with the current understanding of the aircraft contaminated air supply issue. A brief review of a recent French Bureau d'Enquêtes et d'Analyses (BEA) report as well as a collation of key recommendations and findings by bureaus of air safety was also undertaken.

Findings: Fume events associated with the aircraft air supply are not uncommon. A review of 6 A320 family aircraft reporting fumes at various transient phases of flight, commonly described as a dirty sock type odour, reported that no fault could be found. While there are a number of common features identified with these events as well as fume events in general, the report identified a reluctance to directly address air supplies contaminated with oil leakage and an incomplete appreciation of the wider implications of such exposures.

Limitations: This review has not been afforded access to the complete files used in the investigations.

Practical Implications: This brief review has wide implications for all aircraft using bleed air for ventilation purposes.

Social Implications: The findings outlined in this brief review are relevant to all aircrew, passengers and the aviation industry.

Value and Originality: The value of this review has the potential to change the way the aviation industry supplies air to aircraft crew and passengers globally.

Keywords (ACA Component Head)

AIB report, fume event, oil fumes, impairment, flight safety

1 Introduction

Contaminated air events sourced to the aircraft air supply, commonly known as fume events (FE) are not uncommon. These date back to the 1950s, when synthetic jet engine oils were introduced to higher performing gas turbine en-

How to cite this paper (ISO 690, Harvard): MICHAELIS, Susan, 2021. Air Accident Bureau Incident Reports - Case Study Review. *Aircraft Cabin Air International Conference 2021 (Online, 15-18 March 2021)*. London, UK: GCAQE. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457066>

Related presentation: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4730428>

Review process: Editorial review. The corresponding author is marked with *.

gines. There have been increasing FE reports, particularly over the last few decades. More recently there have been many FEs reported on the A320 family of aircraft.

There have been an increasing number of Air Investigation Bureau (AIB) reports published in the last 2 decades related to aircraft contaminated supply air and FEs. These have varied from the more common brief reports to a number of very extensive reports. There are recurring themes identified in the finding and analysis, with some publishing recommendations that exhibit a common pattern.

Many of these reports identify that the FEs were non-visible, involved some degree of impairment, were transient in nature, with numerous other common features including that no fault was found (NFF) after maintenance investigations.

2 Methodology

The AAIB report into an Airbus A320-232 G-EUYB incident that took place in 2019 was reviewed to align common themes highlighted with the wider understanding involving the aircraft contaminated bleed air FEs (AAIB 2020). The AAIB report included the main FE as well as 5 other similar FEs in which no maintenance fault was identified. A summary of key findings and recommendations from various international AIBs will be provided along with a brief review of a recent BEA report involving a fume event on an A330.

3 Findings

Over 3100 smell, smoke or fume (SSF) events were reported to the aviation regulator (CAA) over the previous 5 years with 107 fume events reported to the AAIB during this same period. The operator of the incident flight had reported 536 SSF events to the regulator of which 398 occurred on the A320 series of aircraft. The operator recorded approximately 880 odour and FEs in the 12 months to March 2020.

Of the 6 FEs investigated some of the common features included 4 were described as sweaty socks, all involved fumes only without visible smoke or haze, 5 occurred during start up climb and or approach, with one occurring during the cruise only. 2 and 1 of the FE flights involved a FE prior and after the main FE respectively. Impairment involving the pilots and cabin crew occurred in 1 and 3 of the 6 FE flights respectively, with the first officer becoming incapacitated due to nausea and vomiting. No passengers reported adverse effects. Throat irritation was most commonly reported, along with a range of other irritant effects, gastrointestinal effects, dizziness and headaches. The captain and first officer involved in the main event were both involved in serious prior FE incidents 9 months and 7 weeks respectively prior to the main incident flight. In all cases no fault was said to have been found after maintenance investigations. However, in 1 case an engine was replaced, another was reported to have possibly been overfilled with oil on the previous flight, another was released for service after a FE on the previous flight. The aircraft in the main event was released for service after NFF, with 4 further FEs reported on the same aircraft. Several features involved the FEs commonly occurring at around 4000 feet on the approach and in the circuit before landing, FEs occurring during the climb after damp/rain conditions or being parked overnight. The fumes were mostly transient, of short duration and in 4 of the 6 flights the fumes appeared, disappeared and then reappeared at various phases of flight. Various other common features were noted as shown in [Figure 1](#).

4 Discussion

Compressor generated pressurised air is used to seal the oil bearing chambers in aircraft as shown in [Figure 2](#). The use of pressurised oil bearing seals provides the mechanism for low level oil leakage past the seals in normal flight (Michaelis 2018, Howard 2018). Breathing air in most aircraft is sourced from the compressor and therefore oil passing over the seals in the area of the compressor, has a path to enter the cabin air supply if leakage or emissions occur prior to the air off-take location (Howard 2018).

Figure 1 Features identified in the AAIB report (AAIB 2020).

Figure 2 Typical oil bearing chamber (Exxon Mobil 2016).

A range of short and longer term health effects associated with contaminated aircraft air supplies and fume events include neurological, neurobehavioural, cardio, respiratory, gastrointestinal, irritant and other general effects (Michaelis 2017).

There are however various discrepancies in the AAIB overview of the common features of FEs that are shown in figure 1. Several examples include the following as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Comparison of selected AAIB report findings and Case study review.

AAIB report (AAIB 2020)	Air accident bureau incident reports - Case study review (Michaelis 2021)
FEs associated with acute irritant effects.	Fumes associated with a range of toxic and hazardous effects (Michaelis 2017, ECHA 2008). A range of long-term effects are well documented (Winder 2005).
Most FEs do not have adverse effects on pilots.	Many reports identify adverse effects in pilots as well as cabin crew (Michaelis 2017, Michaelis 2010, BFU 2014).
FEs lead to a stressful situation which leads to physiological effects.	Checklists often address smoke only, education and training on FEs is lacking and a range of adverse effects are associated with the Fumes (BFU 2018, ICAO 2015, ECHA 2008, Michaelis 2017). Oil Material safety Data Sheets list a range of adverse effects.
FEs often have characteristic dirty sock/pungent smell	Oils and heat or moisture generate carboxylic acids, which have a known dirty sock odour (ASHRAE 2012, Johnson 2018).
Fumes are transient and therefore a sample cannot be captured.	There are no detection systems on board aircraft to capture FEs in real-time & there are a wide range of compounds associated with fumes captured in ad-hoc monitoring programs and pyrolysis studies (BFU 2014, Chen 2021).
Fumes often associated with humidity and various phases of flight.	Oil exposed to water (Hydrolysis) causes ester base stock to revert to carboxylic acids (ASHRAE 2012, Johnson 2018).
Very often cannot identify source for transient FEs.	Very little oil required to generate fumes & investigation techniques inadequate for the more common transient non-visible FEs as maintenance practices more appropriate for smoke events or failure conditions (Vera-Barcelo 2013, Howard 2018).
FEs occur more often during Start up, climb, descent/approach phase of flight.	Oil seals are less effective at these times with changing or reduced pressures over seals (Michaelis 2018).

Over the last 2 decades there have been an increasing number of AIB investigations and reports. While most are of a brief nature, some have been more extensive. There are an increasing number of important findings with over 50 recommendations made in 16 reports from 10 countries. These recommendations cover a variety of areas including airworthiness, maintenance and certification, protocols during and post FEs, international database, research addressing the oils, contaminants and effects on human health and detection and warning systems.

A French BEA investigation involving possible exhaust gases on lineup, oil leakage and partial incapacitation, reviewed a number of factors common to oil fumes exposures (BEA 2020). Several findings related to oil fumes were correctly outlined, however there were numerous areas showing an incomplete understanding of such exposures and oil leakage. This is a common deficiency in many AIB investigations, including both reports investigated in this review.

5 Summary and Conclusions

Despite there being a number of common features related to contaminated air and oil fume events as outlined in the AAIB report, there is no mention or a possible reluctance of oil fumes being mentioned as the likely cause of the transient FEs. The FEs are consistent with exposure to oil fumes. A lack of appreciation on how and why oil leakage and FEs occur is evident. There is a reliance on failure conditions leading to oil leakage, while leakage in normal operation is not given due consideration. Sensors and supply air filtration are clearly required. There is also an under appreciation of the health effects associated with such exposures and a clear need for a medical protocol to be utilized after FEs occur.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AAIB	Air Accidents Investigation Branch, UK
AIB	Air Investigation Bureau
FE	Fume Event
NFF	No Fault Found
SSF	Smell, Smoke or Fume

Acknowledgements

No financial support was provided for this case study review. The author declares that no conflict of interest exists with the results and conclusions presented in this paper. Publication ethics have been observed.

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